

Article

Integrating Citizen Perspectives into Climate Risk Management and Adaptation Strategies

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Abstract: Climate crisis is well evidenced with important consequences at the local scale. Often, climate risk assessment and adaptation measures at the national or regional level do not account for local climate impacts and cross-sectoral challenges. This paper presents the findings of a year-long study involving the local community of the Municipality of Sitia in Crete (Greece) in climate change risk assessment and adaptation policymaking. Three coherent workshops produced a citizen-based risk assessment and revealed stakeholders' perceptions about existing policies from the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan of Crete (RCCAPC), addressing climate change impacts on vulnerable economic sectors (agriculture, water, biodiversity, tourism), their effectiveness or lack thereof. It also looks at their ability to suggest solutions regarding the effects of climate change. The study emphasizes how climate hazards affect Sitia's social elements and, in order to find any differences, reported perceptions were compared with the RCCAPC. By doing so, the research breaks new ground in the participatory formulation of environmental policies that are well-informed, place-based, and climate-sensitive, reflecting a dynamic synthesis of public engagement, scientific research, and practical policy implementation.

Keywords: climate risk; citizen engagement; perceptions; participatory policymaking; climate adaptation; Sitia; Crete

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1. Introduction

The escalation of climate change has heightened the frequency and severity of extreme climate hazards across different regions globally [1,2]. However, the impacts of these events are felt locally and pose significant threats to ecosystems, infrastructures [3,4], and human health (both physical and mental) [5]. Public perception, being susceptible to the effects of climate change [6,7], is affected drastically, altering the needs of citizens. In the Mediterranean region, where the case study of the Municipality of Sitia (Crete Island) is located, local communities have been struggling to adapt to a pronounced decrease in precipitation, especially during the warm season, which is projected to continue [8]. The coasts are facing increased risks, including erosion and flooding from extreme events. Like marine storms and hurricanes, that appear in the Mediterranean basin, also known as medicanes [9].

Moreover, a significant warming trend is indicated, with temperatures rising faster than in many other inhabited regions [10]. All the aforementioned phenomena cause severe risks to public health [11], agriculture [12–14], water resources [15], biodiversity [16,17], tourism [18,19], cultural heritage [20], and socio-economic issues [21].

Multiscale actions for mitigating or adapting to climate change are essential [22,23], emphasizing the critical nature of climate hazards and the necessity of strong policies and measures. Despite many efforts, the evolving dynamics of climate change present compelling challenges to local communities worldwide [24]. Top-down policy-making approaches, conceived and implemented at EU, national or regional scales, have inadequately addressed these localised climate hazards [25,26]. These communities have unique socio-cultural characteristics, vulnerabilities, and resources, which require tailored approaches [27]. Public perception, regarding climate change, its impact and ways to deal with it, is a significant indicator of the effectiveness of such measures and how to model them in the future [28]. Generic policies may not take these factors into account, as local perceptions are not considered, often leading to gaps in implementation and maladaptation [29]. Participatory techniques, like surveys and workshops, can be used to efficiently collect local stakeholders' perceptions [30,31].

The current study introduces a participatory approach to identifying and assessing place-based climate adaptation solutions and integrating scientific expertise and stakeholder perceptions with existing policy frameworks at the regional scale. It is part of the NEVERMORE (New Enabling Visions and Tools for End-Users and Stakeholders Thanks to a Common Modelling Approach towards a Climate Neutral and Resilient Society) project, which seeks to develop an integrated impact assessment framework for evaluating climate change impacts and mitigation and adaptation policies, with the inclusion of local knowledge through the involvement of stakeholders in five case studies, the Municipality of Sitia being one of them [32]. The study implements a series of coherent citizen-based activities (a) conducting participatory climate risk assessment following a qualitative approach, (b) implementing place-based vulnerability assessment and (c) critical appraisal of regional and localized adaptation options. The municipality of Sitia in eastern Crete is a climate hotspot that is highly vulnerable to extreme events due to climate change and where local policies still need to be developed [33]. By promoting a participatory approach and enhancing stakeholders' understanding of current policies and policy gaps, as well as mutual understanding of different sectoral interests, this study paves the way for ownership and consensus on bottom-up policymaking.

1.1. Participatory Approaches in Climate Risk Assessment

Several studies have highlighted the importance of participatory processes in empowering communities, including vulnerable groups, to make decisions about their adaptation to climate change [34,35]. Participatory approaches can be used at all levels of risk assessment and policymaking, yet outsourcing adaptation tasks to lower levels of government, such as regions, can make adaptation more feasible to local circumstances and requirements [36]. Ref. [37] investigated ways to jointly produce climate services in order to facilitate risk-informed decision-making and adaptation measures. Through surveys, interviews, and workshops, they sought to identify the opportunities and problems of co-production processes based on six case studies in Northern and Central Europe.

Participatory methods for climate risk assessment and planning, such as workshops, surveys, interviews, group discussions, and guided sessions, can be scientifically based, such as indicator-driven and secondary data-enabled [38] approaches, and help obtain stakeholder perception of climate change risks and institutional evidence [39,40] and identify present social and environmental challenges, as well as the key consequences that

climate change is predicted to have on a social–ecological system [41,42]. In this context, ref. [43] analyzed the advantages and limitations of local perceptions of climate change with the possibility of making use of new scientific methods, highlighting the importance of addressing previously overlooked geographic or climatic hotspots, as in the case study of Sitia.

In the framework of assessing adaptation and risk management plans, refs. [42,44] helped develop common knowledge among stakeholders about the current policy situation, identify possible drivers and barriers to change, and propose solutions. Participatory methods have also been used to incorporate stakeholder perspectives into a model evaluation without much technical knowledge [45–48], increasing the credibility of the final results by aligning with stakeholders' perception and using local expertise throughout the model development and application process.

The current study examined the ability of local stakeholders in Sitia to recognize the impacts of climate change and, thus, climate change itself, highlighting the localization and severity of these hazards in vulnerable sectors, as indicated by them, of this small and diverse community. Based on this qualitative risk assessment, the ability of stakeholders to offer potential solutions for the consequences of those occurrences was also examined. The influence on the social dimensions of two of the most imminent climate hazards for the case study of Sitia was also recognized. Moreover, their familiarity with a set of policies from the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan of Crete (RCCAPC) [49] was validated in terms of whether they are in place, whether they are properly applied, and whether they are effective in their region. These objectives were achieved via participatory activities (workshops), emphasizing the significance of these processes in actively involving stakeholders in the policymaking process [50]. Finally, a step-by-step comparison of the recorded perceptions and the RCCAPC was performed to identify any discrepancies.

1.2. Sitia's Characteristics and Challenges

The Municipality of Sitia is situated on the northeastern corner of Crete (Figure 1), with a population of circa 20,438 inhabitants [51]. The area's economy is traditionally based on agriculture, although production is often limited due to the stony and mountainous terrain. Also known as the "City of Olive Oil" [52], Sitia produces olive oil and multiple Protected Destination of Origin (PDO) products. The quality of olive trees and olive oil, including factors like acidity, is intricately linked to farming practices and prevailing climate conditions, emphasising the critical need to develop resilient agricultural strategies to safeguard local food security. The Sitia Geopark has been part of the UNESCO Global Geoparks Network since 2015 and occupies an area of 516.7 km² [53,54].

Figure 1. Sitia in Europe.

1.2.1. Climate Assessment

Sitia can be considered a “climate hotspot”. It is one of the most exposed European regions to thermal drought, as it experiences almost 300 sunshine days per year with only a few rain events [55]. These circumstances impact freshwater levels, especially during summer when needs increase due to tourism and agriculture [56]. Thus, one of the main challenges for the region is maintaining sufficient and sustainable freshwater resources of high environmental quality [8]. Furthermore, sustained high winds are noteworthy in the region’s eastern part. Another major challenge for Sitia is coastal erosion (especially relevant for the southern coasts) [57], which has accelerated in recent years. The projection for sea level rise in 2100 is more than one meter [58], and storm surges are expected to cause unforeseen alterations in the shoreline owing to erosion [59]. The region has experienced a notable increase in extreme weather events [8], including rapidly spreading wildfires, intense cloudbursts, heavy thunderstorms (Table 1), floods [60], heat waves, and strong winds (Figure 2).

Table 1. Catastrophic incidents of hail recorded in Sitia [61].

Weather Event	Date	Location	Description
Hail	14 November 2010	Sitia, Lasithi Region	Damaged crops and forests
Hail	20 September 2016	Sitia/Xerolimni, Lasithi Region	Hail up to 3.5 cm in size
Hail	20 September 2016	Sitia/Kellaria, Lasithi Region	Damaged crops and forests

Figure 2. Events of floods, extreme rainfall and wildfires in the Municipality of Sitia.

1.2.2. Sectoral Challenges

In terms of renewable energy, 52% of Crete’s installed wind turbines are located in the hilly areas of Sitia [62–64]. However, the siting of these installations, particularly in forested lands [65], has sparked public dissatisfaction and concerns about the potential for wildfire risks during the summer months. Furthermore, the extensive high-voltage transmission network, which facilitates the export of excess power, poses additional wildfire risks. Moreover, the area enjoys a rich biodiversity (Figure 3a) [66]. However, there is a looming threat to endemic species due to the adverse effects of declining climate conditions and water stress, compounded by the encroachment of invasive species.

Figure 3. (a) The Natura 2000 areas of the Municipality of Sitia, (b) Geomorphological map of the Municipality of Sitia.

Transportation infrastructure in the region faces significant climate-related challenges, with many mountainous roads (Figure 3b) experiencing recurrent flooding and degradation, primarily due to soil erosion and inadequate maintenance. These issues substantially pose accessibility risks, especially for remote communities, highlighting the governance challenges in managing and maintaining road networks effectively. A very rough landscape contributes to sporadic telecommunication coverage, presenting significant hurdles to the region's digitalisation efforts, which may limit the implementation of technological solutions to combat climate change impact, such as sensors to monitor the area.

The region's economy, heavily reliant on agriculture and tourism [67], is highly exposed to climate variability. Furthermore, the UNESCO Geopark dominates the region (Figure 1), not only serving as a significant cultural and social asset but also showcasing the unique geological features of the land and its vast network of archaeological sites [68]. As such, the preservation of these natural and cultural treasures is paramount in the region's pursuit of sustainable development and climate resilience.

1.2.3. Social–Psychological Challenges

Another important sector of vulnerability is associated with mental health impacts due to climate change as a result of extreme weather events [69]. A wide range of research has investigated the psychological impacts of climate-related risks, such as post-traumatic stress disorder, sadness, anxiety, and even the worsening of psychotic symptoms and suicidal thoughts. Along with these mental health implications, sensations of ecological anxiety (i.e., fear and worry about projected threats to significant ecosystems) and ecological mourning (i.e., sadness in response to ecological loss) due to climate change are increasing. Ref. [70] highlights the importance in the case of Greece of fostering preventive measures, especially for the young population, through educational institutions and teachers. In fact, teachers are on the front line and serve as first responders, since they are experiencing students' emotional reactions. Furthermore, they could contribute to the implementation of relief techniques or to educating youngsters in adopting effective coping strategies. In Sitia, even though participatory prevention actions are implemented for various psychosocial

problems, such as prevention of addictions (see Self-help Promotion Program <https://www.selfhelp.gr/en/>, accessed on 17 December 2024), there are limited efforts focusing on system-based prevention programs regarding the mental health consequences of climate change, designed and delivered to school communities.

1.2.4. Vulnerabilities Quantification: EU Risk Hub

Table 2 summarizes the findings of the European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre vulnerability index for the Lasithi Region [71], where the Municipality of Sitia is located; it presents a comprehensive view of the vulnerability indices across different dimensions for 2023, from 1 to 10, where 10 is the maximum level of vulnerability.

Table 2. Vulnerability indices and dimensions [72].

Vulnerability Index	NUTS3 Level Indicators	Index Value
Social Vulnerability	Population density	5.5
	Net migration	
	Average distance to healthcare facilities	
	Access to Local Services	
	Young dependency	
	Old dependency	
Economic Vulnerability	NUTS3 GDP per capita vs. country average	7.3
	Gross Value Added (at basic prices—per capita)	
	Power plants per 100,000 inhabitants	
	Patent applications to the EPO	
Political Vulnerability	Regional Quality of Government Index	6.7
Environmental Vulnerability	Proportion of green urban areas against other artificial surfaces	5.2
	Land take intensity	
Physical Vulnerability	Rate of fatalities caused by disasters (20-year moving average per capita)	2.5
	Economic losses caused by disasters as a percentage of GDP (20-year moving average)	
Overall Vulnerability	The average value of the above indices	5.5

1.2.5. Regional Policies for Climate Adaptation in Sitia’s Most Vulnerable Sectors

The Region of Crete, where Sitia is located, has included several Policies and Measures (PaMs) for different sectors in the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan of Crete [49]. Sitia’s most vulnerable sectors are shown in Table 3 and follow the classification of [49], placing them in the highest level of vulnerability.

The PaMs for Tourism address the climate adaptation of tourist facilities and support to deal with extreme phenomena. For Agriculture/Livestock Farming, strategies focus on the mitigation of extreme events and disasters, improving monitoring systems for livestock farming, promoting awareness of climate change among rural professionals and farmers, integrating adaptation planning into agricultural policies based on vulnerability assessments and implementing changes in biological material and cultivation techniques

to better adapt to changing climatic conditions. Regarding the water sector, the existing PaMs aim at sustainable management of water resources. Lastly, Biodiversity's PaMs focus on enhancing understanding and protecting biodiversity, including advancing knowledge of endemic vulnerability and ecosystem services.

Table 3. Vulnerable sectors of Sitia.

Vulnerable Sectors
Tourism
Agriculture
Water
Biodiversity

Facing significant climate hazards, Sitia has a critical need for adaptive, inclusive, and forward-thinking strategies to address climate change impacts, which need to be science-based [6], as well as bottom-up, in order to maximize all types of knowledge. Engaging local communities, leveraging interdisciplinary expertise, and adopting participatory risk-based policymaking can provide a robust framework for enhancing resilience and sustainability in Sitia and similar regions. For the first time, a citizen-based qualitative risk assessment was carried out in the remote region of Sitia using high-resolution climate data to identify localized hazards, solutions, and social impacts. This was something that previous plans or regulations did not, or could not, take into account because of a lack of precise resources and/or local stakeholder awareness.

2. Participatory Climate Adaptation in Sitia

The proposed approach to activities with stakeholders through Local Councils has been guided by the principles of co-creation for policy design, which rely on collective intelligence and creativity. Policy co-design uses visual and tangible tools to directly engage communities, industry organisations, and other government departments, in order to collaborate and design policies to make more informed decisions to meet the community's diverse needs. Co-creation ensures that resulting policies and interventions are relevant, feasible, and effective. In the specific context of policies to tackle climate change, co-creation brings together diverse stakeholders to ensure that policies are grounded in scientific evidence, address societal needs, and promote sustainable and equitable solutions. Ultimately, co-creation generates evidence to inform policymaking while gathering knowledge that may reduce uncertainties around the policy options, helping to achieve a more significant policy impact [73].

Potential stakeholders participating in the Local Council were initially listed by the point of reference for Sitia in the project, i.e., the head of the fire department. This initial phase was called 'stakeholder mapping', and guidelines were provided by the NEVER-MORE partners responsible for engagement and co-design. According to this, local councils should consist of the following:

1. Policymakers, since the project aims to imagine future scenarios and define adaptation and mitigation measures.
2. Academia, given the high scientific and research components of the project.
3. The actors in the most vulnerable economic sectors in each case study.
4. Civil Society, considering the project's relevance to synergies with local realities, and vulnerable groups in particular.
5. Biodiversity representatives, to give voice to an environment-centred perspective.

6. Finally, local media, since this is an important stakeholder group that is seldom actively involved but knows the territory from many angles, and can be essential for disseminating and exploiting the project results.

Another important guideline to follow was to aim for gender balance in the council. Then, Local Councils maintain a flexible structure, according to which new people can join if interested or their expertise is deemed particularly valuable for a consultation. Following this flexibility and openness principle, the early stakeholders named other actors that could provide valuable perspectives to the discussions, and the local council broadened through the snowball sampling effect.

Sitia's Local Council (LC) comprises about 18 stakeholders from all the categories recommended by the NEVERMORE engagement strategy (Figure 4). The civil society associations that accepted an invitation to be part of the council are the Parents and Guardians Association, the Emergency Rescue Volunteers of Crete, the Municipal Organization of Socio-Cultural Development, the Hellenic Red Cross, and a few agricultural cooperatives and activists. The private sector is represented by olive oil producers. Media outlets, such as local radio and newspapers, the Sitia Geopark as the primary natural conservation organisation in the territory, and researchers in Agronomy and Geo-environmental issues from national universities are present. Finally, the policymakers involved are Sitia's municipality, hospital, high school, port, and some nearby municipalities.

Figure 4. Sitia Local Council's composition.

By gathering all the most relevant actors in the territory from a social, political, environmental, and entrepreneurial point of view, we aimed to create a forum for discussion where all voices exposed to climate change impacts could express themselves and, together, make progress in the understanding of this phenomenon and finding adaptation solutions.

2.1. Materials and Methods

Three consultation sessions (Figure 5) were held as part of an initiative to engage local stakeholders for (a) conducting participatory climate risk assessment following a mixed-methods approach, (b) implementing place-based vulnerability assessment and (c) critical appraisal of regional and localized adaptation options.

Figure 5. The three consultations held in Sitia: the previous one sets the stage for the next.

These consultations aimed to combine scientific and local knowledge and create a dialogue between the different stakeholders regarding Sitia’s climate impacts. They allowed stakeholders to share their expertise and perspectives on climate change and existing regional policies on climate adaptation, provided the scientific partners with great insights into local objectives and concerns, and raised stakeholders’ understanding of climate change’s existing and predicted implications in their region. Finally, the sessions aimed to encourage stakeholders to actively participate in a participatory, risk-based policymaking process, allowing them to help build specific resilience measures for their community.

In NEVERMORE, the general topic of each consultation workshop is established by the scientific partners based on what data they need to collect or what project outcome needs to be validated. Similarly, the general structure of the consultations is set by the partners coordinating the codesign activities, while detailed materials and procedures are decided at the case study level. This organisation is guided by the principles of adaptability and flexibility: well-established methodologies are adapted each time according to the goal of the specific activity being undertaken and the familiarity and expertise of stakeholders with the topic to be addressed.

Typically, each consultation informs the subsequent one to progress the discussion in a more focused and solution-driven way (Figure 5) and covers the following structure:

- A restitution of the results of the previous workshop and how they have helped the project progress;
- A presentation/explanation of the topics to be addressed in the current workshop provided by the NEVERMORE technical partners;
- A data collection moment typically organised as a workshop.

As for the three consultations in Sitia reported in this paper, materials to support the interactive and collaborative activities among the stakeholders were planned by the local team of facilitators, who would rely on official information and literature about the territory.

2.2. First Consultation: Participatory Climate Risk Assessment at Priority Sectors

The first consultation was divided into two sessions: a presentation of the current and possible future impacts of climate change on the region of Sitia and a set of collaborative activities to identify the most critical climate hazards for the area, as well as the most vulnerable economic sectors, and to brainstorm possible adaptive interventions. To assess and quantify the multiple risks in the area of interest given the likelihood of a hazard and the determined impact, the risk matrix methodology was followed. To elicit a thorough evaluation of the region’s sensitivity to climate threats and the impact of extreme events within each sector, two activities were prepared, where stakeholders had to fill out two matrixes (Figure 6), first by voting on the most critical sectors for each hazard and then by writing possible adaptive solutions.

Figure 6. (a) Structure of the climate risk matrix, (b) Structure of possible solutions' matrix.

To help stakeholders build a comprehensive understanding of the local context of climate change in the first session, the facilitation team presented basic concepts and terms related to climate change and extreme weather events and then coordinated and supported participatory activities to collect statistical and spatial information in order to build a comprehensive understanding of the local context of climate change. The data collected during this session were used to generate high-resolution climate projections for both near and far-future scenarios, utilising Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios, specifically RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 [6]. These projections provided insights into potential climate trends and their likely impacts on the region and were deemed a valuable starting point for initiating discussion with the stakeholders.

This first consultation fostered dialogue and consensus-building, laying the groundwork for informed decision-making and targeted intervention strategies to enhance climate resilience at the local level. By outlining the sectors affected by climate effects, the exercise helped stakeholders understand the relationship between climate impacts across several domains, such as agriculture, infrastructure, and public health. Furthermore, the visualisations helped stakeholders quickly understand which sectors are most vulnerable to specific types of natural events, and the collaborative approach enabled stakeholders to identify significant areas for intervention and propose innovative solutions to improve climate resilience across several industries.

2.3. Second Consultation: Most Vulnerable Assets to Flood and Drought

The Municipality of Sitia's second local consultation meeting aimed to directly engage local stakeholders in assessing the vulnerability of different socio-economic groups, physical infrastructure, and environmental assets to the threats of flood and drought. These two hazards were pointed out during the first consultation meeting as the most threatening, not only through the process of the risk matrix activity (Figure 7) but also because of the recent (2019, 2022) events that severely affected the area [74].

The participants were informed about the ongoing efforts by the municipality to improve resilience, including infrastructure security and accessibility and ensuring continuous services during power grid failures. The mental health consequences of climate change on children and adolescents, the promotion of psychological well-being of youth, and post-disaster effects were addressed. During the discussion, the need for the implementation of preventive programs and interventions by engaging the members of the school community (families, teachers, and youth) through synergies at the local and national levels was highlighted, specifically, the need to adopt training programs and designate concrete plans of action, involving the general public, with the support of local and national

authorities. In addition, media representatives and volunteers provided an overview of the communication and operational challenges experienced during disaster scenarios. Lastly, environmental advocates noted the adverse effects of human activity on local ecosystems, particularly on river systems, and its exacerbation of flood risks.

Figure 7. Result of the 1st LC meeting, first activity: Risk matrix.

An important tool to gather data on the stakeholders' perspectives on the aforementioned issues was a series of questionnaires. Thus, participants were asked to fill out printed questionnaires containing all the elements, assets and social variables to be studied. A table with the definitions of each social indicator was presented at the end of the questionnaire, followed by a lengthy discussion to ensure stakeholder comprehension. Questions focused on perceived vulnerabilities, aiming to discern which population groups, infrastructure assets, and environmental features were considered at most risk from floods and droughts. The feedback from this consultation process provided the basis for a citizen-based risk assessment for the municipality that could uncover the major weather hazards of the region, as perceived and experienced by its citizens, and how these hazards affect the most prominent work and economic sectors.

2.4. Third Consultation: CCA and DRR Policy Gaps

A round table discussion was held to evaluate existing regulations in key sectors of interest, including tourism, water resources/coastal regions, farming/agriculture, and biodiversity. The primary purpose of this effort was to give stakeholders an overview of the existing policy environment, get their feedback on whether they were aware of the climate-related policies in place at that time and assess their understanding of these matters. Participants were asked to evaluate the success of these policies in the Municipality of Sitia and if they were producing the anticipated results. To collect these data, questionnaires were handed out. These questionnaires were based on the PaMs.

Additionally, stakeholders were encouraged to identify gaps in the existing policies and provide suggestions for enhancing their effectiveness in Sitia. Furthermore, the activity aimed to identify potential synergies between policies across multiple sectors, fostering collaboration and integrated approaches to address common challenges. Through this collaborative assessment of existing policies, stakeholders gained valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of current governance frameworks.

3. Results

3.1. Results of the First Consultation

Throughout the initial activity, one significant debate focused on identifying the most pressing concerns caused by climate change that demand immediate response. Participants identified heatwaves, floods, droughts, wildfires, coastal erosion, and the newly acknowledged threat of landslides as major climatic risks for the region. Furthermore, stakeholders emphasised the need to address the impacts of these risks on human life, highlighting examples of fatalities caused by catastrophes, such as landslides. This conversation spurred stakeholders to underline the significance of taking preventative measures to reduce the effect of climate catastrophes and safeguard vulnerable populations.

Another topic of discussion was that of the economic sectors affected by climate change issues. Stakeholders identified tourism, agriculture, biodiversity, and water resources as sectors particularly vulnerable to climate risks. Additionally, the impact of climate change on coastal and urban areas was highlighted, emphasising the interconnection between environmental changes and socio-economic vulnerabilities. Notably, the conversation sparked lively exchanges regarding the observed increase in sea surface temperatures and its repercussions on local biodiversity and fish populations. Moreover, recent events, such as a wildfire outbreak near Sitia, underscored the urgency of addressing the effects of droughts and heat waves. These insights shed light on the complex interplay between climate change and socio-economic dynamics.

The outcome of the first activity was a climate Risk Matrix (Figure 7) for each sector based on citizens' perceptions. This matrix highlights the different levels of risk that natural hazards pose to different sectors, helps guide preparedness and resilience planning, and serves as a tool for prioritizing mitigation and adaptation strategies in response to potential risks. The colour coding indicates the level of impact: red for significant, yellow for limited/indirect and green for insignificant.

Tourism is significantly affected by natural events, such as floods and heat waves, which can deter tourists and damage infrastructure. Drought, fire, and coastal erosion can also affect the natural beauty of a destination, making it less attractive to visitors. Landslides can cause access problems to tourist destinations. Locals perceive these events as highly disruptive, as they can lead to visible damage to attractions and infrastructure, potentially affecting employment and the local economy. Agriculture and livestock farming also face challenges from these natural events, including heatwaves affecting crop and livestock vitality, floods washing away fertile soil, fires devastating fields, and landslides covering fertile ground. Rural or agricultural communities such as Sitia are likely to experience these hazards as serious threats.

Biodiversity impacts are not always immediately apparent to the general public but, in this case, local stakeholders were able to highlight the risks. Heatwaves, floods, droughts, and wildfires may all damage fragile ecosystems and cause habitat loss. Coastal erosion can also influence biodiversity indirectly. Water resources are another sector with varying levels of hazard risk. The availability of clean water can be reduced by heat waves and droughts. Although not as affected by fires, coastal erosion, landslides, and floods, these events can still indirectly affect water resources through changes in landscape and water flow, while floods can contaminate supplies.

Coastal infrastructure faces its greatest threats from erosion and floods. The gradual erosion of coastlines can directly damage property and land, and flooding can damage the built environment. In addition, heat waves, droughts, and fires, which pose less of a direct threat, can increase the maintenance and operating costs of coastal facilities. Finally, urban fabric, the most affected sector, which includes land, infrastructure, and buildings, is highly sensitive to heat waves, which can exacerbate the urban heat island effect and increase

energy demand. Floods pose a direct risk of extensive infrastructure damage. Drought and fire threats affect resource availability and may spread to urban areas. Coastal erosion and landslides are relatively minor concerns unless urban areas are located near vulnerable coastlines or in hilly regions prone to landslides.

The results of the second activity were the suggestions by local citizens regarding possible solutions for each sector (Figure 8), showing a clear effort to address the specific challenges posed by climate hazards. In the tourism sector, the community’s input indicates a strategic emphasis on constructing hotels that not only meet modern standards of comfort but are also designed with materials and structural norms that can withstand the harsh conditions brought on by heat waves. This demonstrates foresight, ensuring that such infrastructure investments are future-proofed against climate risks. Furthermore, the idea of organizing and disseminating information to visitors during the drought reflects an understanding of the importance of communication in crises to maintain the viability of the sector.

		Possible solutions					
		Tourism	Agriculture/ Livestock farming	Biodiversity	Water resources	Coastal infrastructure	Urban fabric
RISK MATRIX	Heatwave	Construction of hotel units based on the most modern materials and standards of safety specifications in case of natural disasters.	Necessary security elements.	Financial and equipment-wise support for civil protection.	Artificial lakes open tanks for irrigation. Construction of tertiary (extra filtration) wastewater treatment.	Artificial lakes open tanks for rainwater cumulation.	"Respect" by urban planners of the "rules/limits" that nature itself sets and correction of these mistakes.
	Flood	Dam Construction. Establishment of river cleaning.	Promotion of irrigation & Wastewater treatment.		Sewage-water reuse.	Construction of land improvement projects.	New stormwater runoff projects.
	Drought	Organization and information of visitors.	Fire prevention zones.		Use - management of rainwater in the urban fabric.	Exploitation of water from wastewater treatment.	Green energy through Hydrogen technologies.
	Wildfire		Protection of terraces (mainly in agriculture).	Reinforcement of the local Fire Department.			
	Coastal erosion		Water supply network		Projects of placing reefs or breakwaters that will reduce the wave momentum on the coasts.		
	Landslide		Reduction in the imprudent use of pesticides		Building new dams to save water.		
	Water temperature						
	Lack of awareness	The "greener" the accommodation is, the more visitors gets.	Local farmers and producers training.		Awareness from a young age about resource management		Participation of young people in information and awareness actions.

Figure 8. Result of the 1st LC meeting, second activity: Possible solutions.

The suggestions for agriculture and livestock farming demonstrate an acute awareness of the need for climate-resilient agricultural practices. The promotion of irrigation and advanced wastewater treatment suggests a dual approach to flood management, focusing on both the distribution of water for crop irrigation and the prevention of waterborne pollutants that can result from flooding. In addition, the proposal to establish fire protection zones aims to protect not only crops but also the larger landscape that supports agricultural productivity, in the face of wildfires. Regarding preserving biodiversity, citizens seem to prioritise infrastructure and institutional support, such as advocating for financial and logistical assistance for civil protection services during heatwaves. The plea to strengthen local fire departments resonates with a similar theme of preparedness, highlighting the crucial role of well-equipped emergency services in responding to and mitigating the immediate damage caused by wildfires to the local ecosystems.

When addressing water resources, the suggested solutions point to innovative water management strategies. The creation of artificial lakes and open tanks for irrigation proposes a method of harnessing natural water accumulation for agricultural use, which could be particularly effective during periods of drought. Moreover, the concept of tertiary wastewater treatment indicates a progressive approach to maintaining water quality that can protect against pollution, particularly in the aftermath of floods. The input that came from stakeholders concerning coastal infrastructure reveals an understanding of the

delicate balance between development and natural coastal processes. The suggestion to accumulate rainwater in artificial lakes could help mitigate the risk of coastal erosion by reducing the volume of run-off that often contributes to the degradation of coastlines. Land improvement projects could serve to fortify coastal areas against the erosive forces of the sea, while wastewater utilization advocates sustainability.

The suggestions for the urban fabric demonstrate a keen awareness of the need to integrate environmental considerations into urban planning. Stormwater runoff projects indicate a proactive approach to managing excess water in urban areas to prevent flooding. Meanwhile, the integration of hydrogen technologies suggests a pivot towards clean energy sources, which could significantly reduce urban carbon emissions and combat the overarching issue of climate change. All these solutions, shaped by the perceptions and experiences of local citizens, seem to be practical and customised to each sector's specific environmental and social context. In their final statements, stakeholders emphasized a sense of urgency and collective responsibility in addressing climate change issues. They highlighted the importance of immediate action to avert further environmental degradation and the socio-economic consequences of climate-related disasters.

3.2. Results of the Second Consultation

Following the hazard identification activity carried out with stakeholders in the first consultation meeting, a mapping of local stakeholders' perceptions of the impacts of floods, and droughts in particular, was performed, because these were considered the most relevant for the area. This showcased varying degrees of vulnerability across different sectors, revealing insightful contrasts and concerns specific to each hazard. Stakeholders believe that water supply and sanitation systems are extremely vulnerable to floods and droughts. In terms of ecosystems, the concern is remarkably similar for both floods (Figures 9 and 10) and droughts (Figures 11 and 12), with all stakeholders agreeing on the highly likely impacts, indicating their understanding of the fragile balance within ecosystems. Concerns about the Geopark, the designated area for the preservation of natural heritage, is notable, with the majority considering it to be at risk, with a higher expectation of drought as a likely impact compared to floods.

Figure 9. Impacts of floods on the built and natural environment.

Figure 10. Impacts of floods on the built and natural environment (cont.).

Figure 11. Drought impacts physical assets and ecosystems.

Figure 12. Drought impacts physical assets and ecosystems (cont.).

Stable water conditions are crucial for the agriculture and environmental sectors. Both floods and droughts pose a high level of concern for their impact. The labour sector's concerns mirror those of agriculture, aligning with the close ties between the workforce and the health of the agricultural sector. There is a high apprehension of impact from both hazards, though the concern for drought is slightly less compared to that of floods. Tourism's reliance on attractive, stable environmental conditions is clear, with stakeholders showing a high concern for the impacts of drought and flood, and there is a slightly higher worry about the effects of a flood, compared to drought. It is expected that floods will have a significant impact on economic activities across different sectors, with a unanimous consensus. Drought is also a cause of concern, albeit slightly lower when combining the 'very likely' and 'likely' categories.

Local heritage sites are more likely to be affected by floods than droughts, while the population is considered vulnerable to both, with a majority concerned about floods and a similarly high level of concern about droughts. Telecommunications and energy infrastructure show a divided perception, with considerable confidence in their resilience, especially from drought, but they are not immune to the risks. However, stakeholders still acknowledge a significant risk, especially from floods. Vital network infrastructures, such as airports and ports, display a higher concern for flood impact than drought, reflecting the more immediate threat that floods pose to these transport hubs.

Hospitals and schools are exposed to moderate risk from both hazards, indicating a belief in their relative resilience but not discounting the potential for disruption, especially from floods. Critical assets and monuments—important for cultural heritage and infrastructure—show great concern for the impact of floods, with a significant majority considering them very likely, and with a slightly lower, but still considerable, concern about drought. Urban buildings and building infrastructure follow a similar pattern, with a notable concern for the impact of both hazards but with a higher concern for the impact of flooding. In sum, the data reflect a nuanced appreciation among local stakeholders for the varying degrees of threat that floods and droughts pose to different sectors, highlighting the need for tailored risk management strategies for each type of natural disaster.

The following bar charts reflect the community's expectations regarding the social impacts of floods (Figure 13) and droughts (Figure 14), revealing concerns encompassing infrastructure, societal values, and the well-being of vulnerable groups. Starting with public infrastructure service levels, a significant majority perceive floods to have a high likelihood of impact while, on the other hand, they view the impact of drought as slightly less imminent. Access to public infrastructure, such as roads and bridges, appears to be a significant concern in the event of floods, with a majority believing it to be very likely to be impacted, compared to droughts, emphasising the physical damage floods can inflict on such structures. Participatory processes and trust in public bodies are equally considered susceptible to both hazards, albeit with a higher anticipation of impact from floods.

Access to environmental information is expected to be less affected, but is still a concern, especially during floods, when it is very likely to be affected, compared to droughts.

Stakeholders likely anticipate that, during such crises, information will be less accessible. Energy poverty is expected to be more of a consequence of drought, which is very likely, suggesting an expectation that water scarcity could lead to energy shortages, while concern remains high for floods. When it comes to environmental policies and values, there is a robust expectation of impact from floods and a strong expectation for droughts, indicating that stakeholders believe that such events can significantly influence policy decisions and societal attitudes toward the environment. Understanding the risks associated with natural disasters is seen as very likely to be affected by both floods and droughts, indicating that stakeholders feel these events could be a wake-up call for the community.

Figure 13. Results of the questionnaire on the social impacts of flooding.

Figure 14. Results of the questionnaire on the social impacts of drought.

The capacity of social services and community organizations to respond to crises is seen as likely to be tested by both floods and droughts, with floods seen as having a slightly greater impact. This reflects a concern about the strain on local governance and support systems during extreme weather events. Socio-economic assets, representing the broader economic health of the community, are considered to be at significant risk from both floods and droughts, with a slightly higher concern for floods. Finally, the focus on vulnerable groups—the disabled, the elderly, and children—reveals an acute awareness of the heightened risks faced by these groups. There is a unanimous belief in their very likely vulnerability to floods and a very high level of concern for their well-being during droughts. In summary, the survey results capture the multidimensional concerns of local stakeholders about the impact of floods and droughts on social systems, values, and the most vulnerable populations.

3.3. Results of the Third Consultation

The discussion of this meeting encompassed a wide range of topics, each shedding light on the current state of policies and their applicability within the Municipality of Sitia. After conducting an introspective assessment, stakeholders identified significant gaps in their understanding of existing policies in various sectors. Notably, the concept of policy synergies between sectors sparked considerable interest and discussion among participants, highlighting the potential for integrated approaches to address common challenges. Additionally, stakeholders expressed general concern over the lack of representation from higher-ranking local authorities in the collaborative process, advocating for greater inclusivity and engagement in future meetings.

The first bar chart (Figure 15) illustrates local stakeholders' perceptions of climate change policies within the tourism sector. Starting with the question of whether they are aware that specific policies exist, more than half of the stakeholders acknowledged the policies in question and that these were actually in place. Nevertheless, the findings also showed that a sizable section of the population is ignorant of these regulations and, as a result, is not fully aware of all the resources the government has made available to assist them. Moving on to the implementation of these policies, the majority of people do not see them being implemented, despite their belief that they are valid.

Figure 15. Results of the questionnaire: Identification of gaps in existing policies on the tourism sector.

The second bar chart (Figure 16) unveils stakeholders' perceptions of the climate change policies associated with agriculture. A slight majority of the local stakeholders were actually aware of the climate change policies related to agriculture. However, those who were unaware of such policies pointed to a potential gap in policy communication, or perhaps a disconnection between policy formulation and public awareness. The application of agriculture-related policies was viewed more critically. A significant majority did not perceive these policies as being applied. When evaluating the effectiveness of the applied policies, opinions were divided evenly. Half of the stakeholders were convinced of the policies' effectiveness. The other half, however, were sceptical, which could reflect either a lack of tangible results, insufficient impact, or possibly even negative consequences of the policy measures that have been perceived.

Figure 16. Results of the questionnaire: Identification of gaps in existing policies in the agricultural sector.

As depicted in the bar chart of Figure 17, less than half of the stakeholders were informed about the water-related climate change policies identified. This suggests that nearly half the stakeholders are familiar with efforts being made to address water challenges in the context of climate change. On the other hand, an important amount was unaware of these policies, pointing to a need for improved communication and policy visibility. Additionally, the largest proportion do not see these policies being put into action. When it comes to the effectiveness of water policies, the majority of stakeholders seem unconvinced; most respondents do not believe that the policies in place are achieving the intended results. In contrast, few of them felt that these policies were effective, indicating that there was a group within the community that did see positive results from the policies that had been implemented.

Figure 17. Results of the questionnaire: Identification of gaps in existing policies on the water sector.

The fourth and last bar chart (Figure 18) concerning stakeholders' perceptions of biodiversity-related climate change policies displays the community's insights on these environmental strategies. Beginning with the existence of such policies, a significant majority acknowledged their presence, indicating that stakeholders were generally aware of the measures aimed at protecting biodiversity amidst climate change. However, a

substantial number of people were not informed about these policies, which raises questions about public engagement and the visibility of these policies. The application of these policies was viewed with notable scepticism. Some respondents felt that the policies were not being applied, painting a stark picture of inaction. In terms of effectiveness, perceptions are closely divided, with a slight majority not convinced of the impact of the policies.

Figure 18. Results of the questionnaire: Identification of gaps in existing policies on the biodiversity sector.

4. Discussion: Comparison of Perceptions and CRCCAP

The aim of the CRCCAP [49] was to identify and prioritize the necessary measures and actions for the adaptation of the Region of Crete to upcoming climate changes. To this end, a trend analysis was carried out for the main climate indicators, based on climate projections from internationally recognized regional climate models (RCMs). Potential changes in extreme phenomena (floods, heat waves, drought, frost invasions, windstorms) in the region were also studied, by analyzing numerous climate indicators. Subsequently, taking into account the climate changes expected in the future for the Region of Crete, an analysis of the vulnerability of 13 key sectors to climate change was carried out, and the sectors and geographical areas that are expected to be most affected were identified (impact assessment). Based on the sectoral and spatial priorities identified by this process, measures and actions were finally proposed. CRCCAP is used in this comparison, since this is the most recent plan (2022) issued, as well as due to the fact that the scale of its analysis (Region of Crete) is the closest to that being examined in this study (local).

The results from the 1st Consultation meeting, as summarised in the risk matrix (Figure 7), revealed that heatwaves, floods, wildfires, coastal erosion, and landslides are the climate hazards with the most pervasive impact on tourism. Tourism, as indicated in Figure 15, appears to be a sector where appropriate policies exist, but may lack in application and, to a slightly lesser extent, effectiveness. Recommendations for the design and layout of hotel rooms to improve resiliency and sustainability are not consistent with CRCCAP (Table 4), in which the focal points of its measures are the development of bioclimatic amenities and the improvement of energy efficiency in buildings in tourist areas. It appears that improving conditions for visitors to archaeological sites during periods of excessive heat is well addressed in theory but, as mentioned in the results, lacks application/effectiveness of the measure.

Table 4. Comparison of stakeholders' possible solutions and measures in place [49].

Possible Solutions	Correspondence with CRCCAP
Construction of hotel units based on the most modern materials and standards of safety specifications in case of natural disasters.	×
Dam Construction. Establishment of river cleaning.	Partially
Organization and information of visitors.	✓
The “greener” the accommodation is, the more visitors get.	✓
Necessary security elements.	×
Promotion of irrigation and wastewater treatment.	✓
Fire prevention zones.	Partially
Protection of terraces (mainly in agriculture).	×
Water supply network	✓
Reduction in the imprudent use of pesticides	×
Local farmers and producers training.	✓
Financial and equipment-wise support for civil protection.	Partially
Reinforcement of the local Fire Department.	Partially
Artificial lakes/open tanks for irrigation.	Partially
Construction of tertiary (extra filtration) wastewater treatment.	×
Sewage-water reuse.	✓
Use–management of rainwater in the urban fabric.	✓
Projects of placing reefs or breakwaters that will reduce the wave momentum on the coasts.	×
Building new dams to save water.	✓
Awareness from a young age about resource management.	Partially

Regarding agriculture and livestock farming, comparing the risk matrix (Figure 7), stakeholder perceptions (Figure 16), existing policies and suggested possible solutions (Figure 8), it is clear that, although CRCCAP [49] includes economic incentives for farm relocation, improvement of recording systems for critical parameters, knowledge dissemination, and promotion of climate-resilient practices and varieties, there are significant gaps in the current program, like improving irrigation and wastewater treatment, safeguarding terraces, and lowering the usage of pesticides (Table 4). Instead, CRCCAP focuses more on reinforcing genetic material banks for native species and provides incentives for low-input farming systems. In addition, targeted information campaigns and training seminars are mentioned for better education of farmers about resistant crop varieties, sustainable farming practices, and soil management strategies that take into account the region's changing climate.

Regarding the water sector, existing policies at the time included sustainable management strategies aimed at the efficient and rational use of irrigation water. Stakeholder perceptions (Figure 17) suggest recognition of the existence of water-related policies, but substantial doubt about their application and effectiveness. The proposed measures (Figure 8), such as the construction of artificial lakes and open tanks for irrigation and rainwater management in urban areas, the reuse of wastewater, and the creation of reefs or breakwaters that reduce wave momentum on the coasts (Table 4), complement existing efforts, such as the construction of new wastewater treatment plants and the control of groundwater extraction. Existing measures (CRCCAP) primarily focus on monitoring groundwater

bodies, modernising water supply networks, and integrating protection zones into spatial planning frameworks.

The existing biodiversity policies encompassed raising awareness, protecting and enhancing biodiversity to adapt to and mitigate climate impacts, and monitoring invasive species [46]. Stakeholder perceptions (Figure 18) and suggested solutions (Figure 8) point to the need for more focused action to improve civil protection and address the impacts of climate change, aligned with existing actions to protect landscapes, ecosystem services, and biodiversity in the region. For instance, while stakeholders propose financial and equipment support for civil protection and reinforcement of the local Fire Department (Table 4), existing measures (CRCCAP) include conducting climate change impact assessments on landscapes and protected areas and implementing targeted actions to inform and raise awareness about biodiversity adaptation to climate change. While existing policies provide support for modernizing and improving livestock facilities, they identified ongoing challenges regarding animal confinement and highlighted unintended consequences for regional biodiversity.

In the Supplementary Materials, a comprehensive comparison is made by the economic sector between the severity of climate hazards (Tables S7–S12), as perceived by local stakeholders (Figure 7), and the CRCCAP assessment, which led to [49]. This can help to understand the discrepancies between the proposed solutions (Figure 8) and the measures in place. The reason for the discrepancies is that they both originate from a different scale of resolution, with the regionality of CRCCAP taking into account some special climatic conditions that exist in certain areas of the island of Crete, such as frost and snowfall, but are not applicable in the area of Sitia and are, therefore, not investigated. Another reason is that, for the only two hazards commonly studied (drought, heat wave) out of a total of ten, there is a different result in terms of their severity locally and regionally, with the most obvious difference being in the water resources sector (Table 4), coastal infrastructure sector (Table S11) and urban fabric sector (Table S12).

The consultations in Sitia revealed several valuable lessons. First, the community demonstrated a remarkable ability to engage in forward-thinking discussions about the future. Their suggestions for the urban fabric showcased a strong awareness of the importance of integrating environmental considerations into urban planning. Notably, the concept of policy synergies across sectors generated significant interest and discussion, underscoring the potential for integrated approaches to tackle shared challenges. Lastly, it became evident that creating new policies is not sufficient on its own; effective communication of these policies is essential to ensure their success.

Finally, it is important to highlight that the participatory approach in this study exhibited several strengths and weaknesses. Among its strengths, the approach ensured continuity over time, as the local council remains open and flexible while maintaining a core group of stakeholders. This consistency enables a progressive exploration of topics, where each consultation builds upon the previous one. Additionally, the process promotes accountability by demonstrating how stakeholder input is utilized for future work. Another key strength is the comprehensive involvement of all relevant local actors, fostering interactions between citizens, policymakers, and researchers. This triad of collaboration enables mutual learning: citizens gain insights into climate science, modelers enhance their understanding of climate change impacts through local knowledge, and policymakers benefit from both local insights and scientific expertise to craft effective policies.

However, the participatory process also faces challenges. Like many such approaches, it is time-consuming, and the project's timeline often lags behind stakeholders' expectations for tangible results. To address this, local policymakers must explore alternative paths for intervention. Furthermore, the long-term use and the impact of stakeholders' contributions

on policymaking remain outside the scope of the current paper. Assessing this would require a longitudinal study beyond the project's duration and depends significantly on political will. Nonetheless, from a methodological perspective, the project offers an exemplary framework for other regions, not by prescribing solutions but by showcasing effective methods to develop them.

5. Conclusions

The present research found a crucial need for adaptable, participative measures to mitigate climate threats in the Municipality of Sitia, Crete. Integrating local knowledge with scientific research and policymaking provides a unique chance to build comprehensive, context-specific strategies to address the various issues posed by climate change. This collaborative approach not only empowers local communities but also ensures that policies and procedures are based on the realities of those most vulnerable to climate hazards. Moving forward, the Municipality of Sitia and other areas facing similar challenges may benefit from cultivating multi-stakeholder partnerships that emphasize shared responsibility and collaborative action in navigating the complexities of climate adaptation and sustainability.

The findings highlight the importance of engaging local stakeholders in the policymaking process to ensure that policies are not only data-driven but also resonate with the lived experiences and insights of the community. By integrating such participatory processes, policies can be more effective and relevant and promote sustainable, climate-adaptive practices. The study's emphasis on local engagement in addressing climate hazards contributes to a more dynamic, democratic, and inclusive approach to policymaking. As a result, policies formulated through this method are better able to increase community resilience and address the specific needs and conditions of the Municipality of Sitia.

The consultations conducted throughout the research have led to an understanding of the climate-related risks and challenges that Sitia's citizens face. These discussions have also highlighted the potential gaps in existing policies for tourism, agriculture, water management, and biodiversity. These findings underscore the importance of developing targeted, sector-specific policies that can bridge these gaps and further highlight the critical need for adaptation measures that can counter the expected impacts of climate hazards. The research also serves as a stimulus for policy development, calling for innovative measures that take into account the specificities of local conditions and vulnerabilities. Therefore, the policy recommendations that emerge from this study by local stakeholders are not only reactive to climate events but proactive, aiming to be forward-looking and inclusive in their approach in order to effectively mitigate climate risks and build long-term resilience.

In comparing local perceptions of climate hazards in Sitia with the region-wide CRC-CAP assessment, notable differences emerged due to spatiotemporal scales, with certain hazards (e.g., frost) being irrelevant locally, whereas the impacts of other relevant hazards (e.g., droughts, heat-waves, floods) were downrated at the regional scale. A participatory approach involving citizens, policymakers, and researchers fostered continuity, accountability, and mutual learning, though it proved time-consuming and its long-term policy impact remains uncertain without sustained political support. Nonetheless, the study underscored the value of integrating local insights into broader assessments, emphasizing not only the need for the creation of new policies but also the importance of effectively communicating them, and provides a replicable framework for collaborative climate adaptation efforts in other regions.

In future work, the results of additional case studies will be incorporated, resulting in integrated assessment modelling (IAM) software for scientific validation. In conclusion, this research highlights that national and/or regional PaMs do not always meet local needs. It also highlights the transformative potential of citizen engagement in policymak-

ing, illustrating how participatory, cross-cutting methodologies can lead to more resilient communities. The Municipality of Sitia's ongoing journey towards participatory risk-based policymaking can provide valuable lessons for other regions, demonstrating the importance of collaborative, inclusive governance and the collective action required for effective climate adaptation and sustainable development.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/su17041382/s1>, Table S1. Questionnaire: Gaps identification of policies in Tourism sector. Table S2. Questionnaire: Gaps identification of policies in Biodiversity sector. Table S3. Questionnaire: Gaps identification of policies in Agriculture/Livestock farming sector. Table S4. Questionnaire: Gaps identification of policies in Water resources sector. Table S5. Questionnaire: Risk assessment of environmental and societal impacts of droughts and floods. Table S6. Policies and Measures for sectors of interest from Regional climate change adaptation plan of Crete (2022). Table S7. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Tourism Sector, regarding risk matrix. Table S8. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Agriculture/Livestock farming Sector, regarding risk matrix. Table S9. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Biodiversity Sector, regarding risk matrix. Table S10. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Water resources, regarding risk matrix. Table S11. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Coastal infrastructure, regarding risk matrix. Table S12. Comparison between stakeholders' perception and Crete's Regional climate change adaptation plan for the Urban fabric, regarding risk matrix. Table S13. Comparison of stakeholders' possible solutions and measures in place. Figure S1. Outcome of the 1st LC meeting: risk matrix and possible solutions. Figure S2. 2nd LC meeting.

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References

1. AghaKouchak, A.; Chiang, F.; Huning, L.S.; Love, C.A.; Mallakpour, I.; Mazdiyasn, O.; Moftakhari, H.; Papalexioiu, S.M.; Ragno, E.; Sadegh, M. Climate Extremes and Compound Hazards in a Warming World. *Annu. Rev. Earth Planet. Sci.* **2020**, *48*, 519–548. [[CrossRef](#)]

2. Arnell, N.W.; Brown, S.; Gosling, S.N.; Gottschalk, P.; Hinkel, J.; Huntingford, C.; Lloyd-Hughes, B.; Lowe, J.A.; Nicholls, R.J.; Osborn, T.J.; et al. The impacts of climate change across the globe: A multi-sectoral assessment. *Clim. Chang.* **2016**, *134*, 457–474. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Clarke, B.; Otto, F.; Stuart-Smith, R.; Harrington, L. Extreme weather impacts of climate change: An attribution perspective. *Environ. Res. Clim.* **2022**, *1*, 012001. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Cramer, W.; Guiot, J.; Fader, M.; Garrabou, J.; Gattuso, J.-P.; Iglesias, A.; Lange, M.A.; Lionello, P.; Llasat, M.C.; Paz, S.; et al. Climate change and interconnected risks to sustainable development in the Mediterranean. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **2018**, *8*, 972–980. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Ma, T.; Moore, J.; Cleary, A. Climate change impacts on the mental health and wellbeing of young people: A scoping review of risk and protective factors. *Soc. Sci. Med.* **2022**, *301*, 114888. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Bostrom, A.; Hayes, A.L.; Crosman, K.M. Efficacy, Action, and Support for Reducing Climate Change Risks. *Risk Anal.* **2019**, *39*, 805–828. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. van Valkengoed, A.M.; Perlaviciute, G.; Steg, L. From believing in climate change to adapting to climate change: The role of risk perception and efficacy beliefs. *Risk Anal.* **2024**, *44*, 553–565. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Golemi, A.M.; Karakitsou, E.; Karozis, S.; Markantonis, I.; Politi, N.; Sfetsos, A.; Vlachogiannis, D.; Kapetanakis, P. How Accurate Climate Information Can Help the Climate Adaptation in Regional Scale: The Case Study of Sitia. *Environ. Sci. Proc.* **2023**, *26*, 170. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Miglietta, M.M.; Rotunno, R. Development mechanisms for Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones (medicanes). *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **2019**, *145*, 1444–1460. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Zittis, G.; Almazroui, M.; Alpert, P.; Ciais, P.; Cramer, W.; Dahdal, Y.; Fnais, M.; Francis, D.; Hadjinicolaou, P.; Howari, F.; et al. Climate Change and Weather Extremes in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East. *Rev. Geophys.* **2022**, *60*, e2021RG000762. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Linares, C.; Díaz, J.; Negev, M.; Martínez, G.S.; Debono, R.; Paz, S. Impacts of climate change on the public health of the Mediterranean Basin population—Current situation, projections, preparedness and adaptation. *Environ. Res.* **2020**, *182*, 109107. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
12. Fraga, H.; Moriondo, M.; Leolini, L.; Santos, J.A. Mediterranean Olive Orchards under Climate Change: A Review of Future Impacts and Adaptation Strategies. *Agronomy* **2021**, *11*, 56. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Abd-Elmabod, S.K.; Muñoz-Rojas, M.; Jordán, A.; Anaya-Romero, M.; Phillips, J.D.; Jones, L.; Zhang, Z.; Pereira, P.; Fleskens, L.; van der Ploeg, M.; et al. Climate change impacts on agricultural suitability and yield reduction in a Mediterranean region. *Geoderma* **2020**, *374*, 114453. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Aguilera, E.; Díaz-Gaona, C.; García-Laureano, R.; Reyes-Palomo, C.; Guzmán, G.I.; Ortolani, L.; Sánchez-Rodríguez, M.; Rodríguez-Estévez, V. Agroecology for adaptation to climate change and resource depletion in the Mediterranean region. *A review. Agric. Syst.* **2020**, *181*, 102809. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Trambly, Y.; Llasat, M.C.; Randin, C.; Coppola, E. Climate change impacts on water resources in the Mediterranean. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* **2020**, *20*, 83. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Aurelle, D.; Thomas, S.; Albert, C.; Bally, M.; Bondeau, A.; Boudouresque, C.-F.; Cahill, A.E.; Carlotti, F.; Chenuil, A.; Cramer, W.; et al. Biodiversity, climate change, and adaptation in the Mediterranean. *Ecosphere* **2022**, *13*, e3915. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Newbold, T.; Oppenheimer, P.; Etard, A.; Williams, J.J. Tropical and Mediterranean biodiversity is disproportionately sensitive to land-use and climate change. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* **2020**, *4*, 1630–1638. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Torres, C.; Jordà, G.; de Vilchez, P.; Vaquer-Sunyer, R.; Rita, J.; Canals, V.; Cladera, A.; Escalona, J.M.; Miranda, M.Á. Climate change and its impacts in the Balearic Islands: A guide for policy design in Mediterranean regions. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* **2021**, *21*, 107. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Belias, D.; Rossidis, I.; Valeri, M. Tourism in Crisis: The Impact of Climate Change on the Tourism Industry. In *Tourism Risk*; Valeri, M., Ed.; Emerald Publishing Limited.: Leeds, UK, 2022; pp. 163–179.
20. Sesana, E.; Gagnon, A.S.; Ciantelli, C.; Cassar, J.; Hughes, J.J. Climate change impacts on cultural heritage: A literature review. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Clim. Chang.* **2021**, *12*, e710. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Sarkar, N.; Rizzo, A.; Vandelli, V.; Soldati, M. A Literature Review of Climate-Related Coastal Risks in the Mediterranean, a Climate Change Hotspot. *Sustainability* **2022**, *14*, 15994. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. European Commission. *The European Green Deal*; COM(2019) 640 Final; European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2019.
23. Masson-Delmotte, V.; Zhai, P.; Pirani, A.; Connors, S.L.; Péan, C.; Berger, S.; Caud, N.; Chen, Y.; Goldfarb, L.; Gomis, M.I.; et al. *IPCC, 2023: Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK, 2023.
24. Gallina, V.; Torresan, S.; Critto, A.; Sperotto, A.; Glade, T.; Marcomini, A. A review of multi-risk methodologies for natural hazards: Consequences and challenges for a climate change impact assessment. *J. Environ. Manag.* **2016**, *168*, 123–132. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Doukas, H.; Nikas, A. Decision support models in climate policy. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* **2020**, *280*, 1–24. [[CrossRef](#)]

26. Salvia, M.; Olazabal, M.; Fokaides, P.A.; Tardieu, L.; Simoes, S.G.; Geneletti, D.; De Gregorio Hurtado, S.; Viguié, V.; Spyridaki, N.-A.; Pietrapertosa, F.; et al. Climate mitigation in the Mediterranean Europe: An assessment of regional and city-level plans. *J. Environ. Manag.* **2021**, *295*, 113146. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Aguiar, F.C.; Bentz, J.; Silva, J.M.N.; Fonseca, A.L.; Swart, R.; Santos, F.D.; Penha-Lopes, G. Adaptation to climate change at local level in Europe: An overview. *Environ. Sci. Policy* **2018**, *86*, 38–63. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Chomać-Pierzecka, E. Investment in Offshore Wind Energy in Poland and Its Impact on Public Opinion. *Energies* **2024**, *17*, 3912. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Rogers, N.J.L.; Adams, V.M.; Byrne, J.A. Factors affecting the mainstreaming of climate change adaptation in municipal policy and practice: A systematic review. *Clim. Policy* **2023**, *23*, 1327–1344. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Maioli, V.; Monteiro, L.M.; Tubenchlak, F.; Pepe, I.S.; de Carvalho, Y.B.; Gomes, F.D.; Strassburg, B.B.; Latawiec, A.E. Local Perception in Forest Landscape Restoration Planning: A Case Study From the Brazilian Atlantic Forest. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **2021**, *9*, 612789. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Ducci, M.; Janssen, R.; Burgers, G.-J.; Rotondo, F. Mapping Local Perceptions for the Planning of Cultural Landscapes. *Int. J. E-Plan. Res. (IJEPR)* **2023**, *12*, 1–27. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. NEVERMORE Project Website. Available online: <https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/> (accessed on 31 July 2024).
33. Cissé, G.; McLeman, R.; Adams, H.; Aldunce, P.; Bowen, K.; Campbell-Lendrum, D.; Clayton, S.; Ebi, K.L.; Hess, J.; Huang, C.; et al. Health, Wellbeing, and the Changing Structure of Communities. In *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability, D.C. Roberts Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*; Pörtner, H.-O., Tignor, M., Poloczanska, E.S., Mintenbeck, K., Alegría, A., Craig, M., Langsdorf, S., Lösschke, S., Möller, V., Okem, A., et al., Eds.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK; New York, NY, USA, 2022; pp. 1041–1170.
34. Lund, D. Navigating slow-onset risks through foresight and flexibility in Fiji: Emerging recommendations for the planned relocation of climate-vulnerable communities. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* **2021**, *50*, 12–20. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Palermo, V.; Hernandez, Y. Group discussions on how to implement a participatory process in climate adaptation planning: A case study in Malaysia. *Ecol. Econ.* **2020**, *177*, 106791. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Otto-Banaszak, I.; Matczak, P.; Wesseler, J.; Wechsung, F. Different perceptions of adaptation to climate change: A mental model approach applied to the evidence from expert interviews. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* **2011**, *11*, 217–228. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. André, K.; Swartling, Å.G.; Englund, M.; Petutschnig, L.; Attoh, E.M.N.A.N.; Milde, K.; Lückerrath, D.; Cauchy, A.; Holm, T.B.; Korsbrekke, M.H.; et al. Improving stakeholder engagement in climate change risk assessments: Insights from six co-production initiatives in Europe. *Front. Clim.* **2023**, *5*, 1120421. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Fleming, C.S.; Regan, S.D.; Freitag, A.; Burkart, H. Indicators and participatory processes: A framework for assessing integrated climate vulnerability and risk as applied in Los Angeles County, California. *Nat. Hazards* **2023**, *115*, 2069–2095. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Krkoška Lorencová, E.; Slavíková, L.; Emmer, A.; Vejchodská, E.; Rybová, K.; Vačkářová, D. Stakeholder engagement and institutional context features of the ecosystem-based approaches in urban adaptation planning in the Czech Republic. *Urban For. Urban Green.* **2021**, *58*, 126955. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Guodaar, L.; Bardsley, D.K.; Suh, J. Integrating local perceptions with scientific evidence to understand climate change variability in northern Ghana: A mixed-methods approach. *Appl. Geogr.* **2021**, *130*, 102440. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Ciobanu, N.; Saisel, A.K. Using social–ecological inventory and group model building for resilience assessment to climate change in a network governance setting: A case study from Ikel watershed in Moldova. *Environ. Dev. Sustain.* **2021**, *23*, 1065–1085. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Schernewski, G.; Bartel, C.; Kobarg, N.; Karnauskaite, D. Retrospective assessment of a managed coastal realignment and lagoon restoration measure: The Geltinger Birk, Germany. *J. Coast. Conserv.* **2018**, *22*, 157–167. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Reyes-García, V.; Fernández-Llamazares, Á.; Guèze, M.; Garcés, A.; Mallo, M.; Vila-Gómez, M.; Vilaseca, M. Local indicators of climate change: The potential contribution of local knowledge to climate research. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Clim. Chang.* **2016**, *7*, 109–124. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Leon, C.J.; González, Y.E.L.; Ruggieri, G.; Calò, P. Assessing Climate Change Adaptation and Risk Management Programmes: Stakeholder Participation Process and Policy Implications for Transport, Energy and Tourism Sectors on the Island of Sicily. *Land* **2022**, *11*, 1206. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Allan, A.; Barbour, E.; Nicholls, R.J.; Hutton, C.; Lim, M.; Salehin, M.; Rahman, M.M. Developing socio-ecological scenarios: A participatory process for engaging stakeholders. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2022**, *807*, 150512. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Hedelin, B.; Evers, M.; Alkan-Olsson, J.; Jonsson, A. Participatory modelling for sustainable development: Key issues derived from five cases of natural resource and disaster risk management. *Environ. Sci. Policy* **2017**, *76*, 185–196. [[CrossRef](#)]
47. Harrison, S.; Macmillan, A.; Bond, S.; Stephenson, J. Participatory modeling for local and regional collaboration on climate change adaptation and health. *J. Clim. Chang. Health* **2023**, *12*, 100235. [[CrossRef](#)]

48. Pasquier, U.; Few, R.; Goulden, M.C.; Hooton, S.; He, Y.; Hiscock, K.M. “We can’t do it on our own!”—Integrating stakeholder and scientific knowledge of future flood risk to inform climate change adaptation planning in a coastal region. *Environ. Sci. Policy* **2020**, *103*, 50–57. [CrossRef]
49. Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan of Crete. Region of Crete. 2022. Available online: http://www.promitheasnet.kepa.uoa.gr/wp-content/uploads/Tsompanidis_Presentation_PESPKA_Crete.pdf (accessed on 17 December 2024).
50. Susskind, L.; Kim, A. Building local capacity to adapt to climate change. *Clim. Policy* **2022**, *22*, 593–606. [CrossRef]
51. ELSTAT. *2021 Population and Housing Census*; Hellenic Statistical Authority of Greece: Piraeus, Greece, 2021.
52. Kalarchakis, I. Attribute Analysis and Quality Assessment of Extra Virgin Olive Oil Produced in Sitia, Crete, Greece. Master’s Thesis, Cranfield University, Cranfield Health, Cranfield, UK, 2011.
53. Unesco Sites in Crete. Available online: <https://www.unescositesincrete.gr/en/sitia/> (accessed on 17 December 2024).
54. Fassoulas, C.; Staridas, S.; Perakis, V.; Mavrokosta, C. Revealing the geoheritage of Eastern Crete, through the development of Sitia Geopark, Crete, Greece. *Bull. Geol. Soc. Greece* **2013**, *47*, 1004–1016. [CrossRef]
55. Hellenic National Meteorological Service. Sitia Climatological Data 1960–2010. Available online: http://intranet.emy.gr/emyl/el/climatology/climatology_city?perifereia=Crete&poli=Sitia (accessed on 17 December 2024).
56. Tsikalakis, G.J.; Makrinakis, N.J.; Bourbourakis, P.J.; Neofotistou, E.D. Economic and Sustainable Development in Eastern Crete Through the Lithines Irrigation Dam. *E3S Web Conf.* **2023**, *436*, 04005. [CrossRef]
57. Karathanasi, F.E.; Belibassakis, K.A. A cost-effective method for estimating long-term effects of waves on beach erosion with application to Sitia Bay, Crete. *Oceanologia* **2019**, *61*, 276–290. [CrossRef]
58. Probst, P.; Annunziato, A. *JRC Sea Level Database: Coastal Hazards*; JRC Technical Reports; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2017.
59. Fuggini, C.; Solari, C.; De Stefano, R.; Bolletta, F.; De Maio, F.V. Assessing resilience at different scales: From single assets to complex systems. *Environ. Syst. Decis.* **2023**, *43*, 693–707. [CrossRef]
60. Neofotistou, E.; Tsikalakis, G.; Kafousia, D.; Bourbourakis, P. Temporal Investigation of the Changes in the Quality Parameters of the Surface Water of the River Pantélis-Sitia. In *E3S Web Conf.* **2024**, *585*, 09006. [CrossRef]
61. European Severe Weather Database. Extreme Weather Events Recorded on the Island of Crete. 2022. Available online: <https://eswd.eu/cgi-bin/eswd.cgi> (accessed on 17 December 2024).
62. Gigantidou, A. Crete Power System. In Proceedings of the 4th International Hybrid Power Systems Workshop, Heraklion, Greece, 22–23 May 2019.
63. Gigantidou, A. Renewable energy sources in Crete. In Proceedings of the 2013 IREP Symposium Bulk Power System Dynamics and Control—IX Optimization, Security and Control of the Emerging Power Grid, Rethymno, Greece, 25–30 August 2013.
64. Kaldellis, J.K.; Vlachou, D.S.; Paliatsos, A.G. Twelve Years Energy Production Assessment of Greek State Wind Parks. *Wind Eng.* **2003**, *27*, 215–226. [CrossRef]
65. Korfiati, I.P. Classifying Like a State: Land Dispossession on Eastern Crete’s Contested Mountains. *Antipode* **2020**, *52*, 1331–1350. [CrossRef]
66. Rackham, O.; Moody, J. *The Making of the Cretan Landscape*; Manchester University Press: Manchester, UK, 1996.
67. Spyridakis, M.; Dima, F. Reinventing traditions: Socially produced goods in Eastern Crete during economic crisis. *J. Rural. Stud.* **2017**, *53*, 269–277. [CrossRef]
68. Koupatsiaris, A.A.; Drinia, H. Exploring Greek UNESCO Global Geoparks: A Systematic Review of Grey Literature on Greek Universities and Future Research Avenues for Sustainable Development. *Geosciences* **2023**, *13*, 296. [CrossRef]
69. Magklara, K.; Kapsimalli, E.; Liarakou, G.; Vlassopoulos, C.; Lazaratou, E. Climate crisis and youth mental health in Greece: An interdisciplinary approach. *Eur. Child Adolesc. Psychiatry* **2024**, *33*, 2431–2435. [CrossRef]
70. Cunsolo, A.; Harper, S.L.; Minor, K.; Hayes, K.; Williams, K.G.; Howard, C. Ecological grief and anxiety: The start of a healthy response to climate change? *Lancet Planet. Health* **2020**, *4*, e261–e263. [CrossRef]
71. The European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Center. Vulnerability Index & Dimensions. 2023. Available online: <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub/#/dashboardvulnerability> (accessed on 17 December 2024).
72. The European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Center. Indicators and References. Available online: https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub/media/vulnerability/Indicators_and_References.pdf (accessed on 31 July 2024).
73. Matti, S.; Ögmundardóttir, H.; Aðalgeirsdóttir, G.; Reichardt, U. Communicating Risk in Glacier Tourism: A Case Study of the Svínafellsheiði Fracture in Iceland. *Mt. Res. Dev.* **2022**, *42*, D1–D12. [CrossRef]
74. Fire Brigade Representative (Municipality of Sitia, Crete, Greece). Personal communication, 2023.

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